

ITALIAN PUBLIC TOURISM SECTOR, BUREAUCRACY AND CHANGE MANAGEMENT
PROCESS: FOUR BUREAUCRATIC ORGANIZATIONAL TYPOLOGIES

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Abstract: This study intends to identify factors that can aid the management of change in the Italian public tourism sector (IPTS). The bureaucracy in IPTS were analysed so as to identify organizational typologies and assess underlying management culture in order to pinpoint the elements that could influence the process of change. The study considered, within IPTS, two regions, one located in southern Italy (Campania Public Tourism Sector – CPTS), and the other in northern Italy (Tuscany Public Tourism Sector – TPTS). The specific data are the Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism - MiBaCT – 2017 and 24 privileged witnesses. The paper reports findings from research in progress. The data were collected through using a questionnaire and statistically analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. The case study allows to identify different typologies of bureaucracy in IPTS (insensitive, sensitive, participated and proactive) and data show the correlation between managerial culture and change management in bureaucracy. The research was limited to only 2 Italian regions out of a total of 22. It is necessary to extend the research to the other regions located in the North and the South of Italy. Possible measures to address operational and cultural problems in the regions have been identified in further research at the national level, analysis of good practices and cross contamination of proactive managers with the participated and insensitive managers. This process can be identified as a change process for the IPTS. It is the first IPTS research paper on the CPTS and TPTS. The analysis may be extended to the entire country. Such a view rejects a stance whereby the bureaucracy could be regarded as ultimately unchangeable. It must instead be seen as under constant development and re-interpretation.

Keywords: Italian Public Tourism Sector, Campania and Tuscany, Factor Analysis, SWOT Analysis, Bureaucratic Theory, Quantitative and Qualitative Approach, Management

Introduction

The IPTS offers an ample chance for experimentation. Its strength is linked to the richness of natural, historical and cultural heritage assets of many regions. On the other hand, the organizational bottlenecks and the high incidence of political decision makers constitute the sector's negative features. A competitiveness-enhancing reform based on professional skills, management capabilities and training needs to be implemented but the process is still ongoing. IPTS, can be a driving force for local development. As an expanding sector, it dynamizes traditional economic activities and enhances local cultural specificities, offering people new opportunities for employment (Gartner C. Cukier J. 2012). Numerous studies (Garcia J.A. 2016) have shown that a timely analysis may be supportive to overcoming obstacles such as:

- poor understanding of local tourist (customer characteristics and market trends by local managers);
- overly large projects (the development of tourism products that can satisfy existing demand);
- adverse environmental impacts (pollution, degradation of natural sites);

- cultural problems (loss of "folklore", characteristics and specifics of the territory);
- managerial culture change management process, characteristics and specificities of the territories.

The purpose of this study is to identify the typologies of bureaucracy in public organizations, underlining the elements that are relevant for change management within CPTS and TPTS. This study examines productivity and efficiency related to the managerial culture. Attention is focused on two regions, one in the North and the other in the South of Italy, and the research outlines change management tools (Beer and Nohria, 2000; By, 2005) capable of contributing to the change management process in IPTS. Secondly, it aims at observing the extent to which the IPTS makes the implementation of organizational change specific. The bureaucracy (Crozier, M. 1964) represents a classic in change management (Merton, 1949; Elliott, J. 1997; Bevir, M. 2009; Hall, C. M. 2005). A change management process in bureaucratic public organization entails realizing strong management procedures that require specific skills, culture, and innovative (Hsu, Tan, Jayaram, Laosirihongthong 2014) attitudes. The managerial culture (Calantone, Gonzalez-Padron, and Hult 2008; Bina 2012) represents a driving factor in motivating and shaping employee behavior (Merton, 1949; Kanter, 1985; Elliott, J. 1997; Raharjo K., Nurjannah, Solimun and Adji A. R. F., 2018). Many authors have suggested that the specificity of public organizations may have effects on change management (Coram and Burnes, 2001; Isett, Glied, Sparer, and Brown, 2012; McNulty and Ferlie, 2004), but there is little empirical evidence regarding the issue of the bureaucracy. Several studies (Boyne, 2006; Karp and Helgø, 2008; Kickert, 2013; Klarner, Probst, and Soparnot, 2008; Rusaw, 2007) stress the matter and context of change, instead of the achievement process. In this way, Kuipers et al. (2013) underline that many studies did not approach the outcomes of a change management (Fernandez and Pitts, 2007; Kickert, 2010). The implementation of change management is strongly dependent on the support of managers. The managers' support is strategic for the evaluation of the degree of change in the entire organization (Gill, 2002; Higgs and Rowland, 2005; Karp and Helgø, 2008; Kotter, 1996). IPTS typically operates under a strict legal framework and strict accountability requirements (Rainey, 2003). Because of this, IPTS tends to avoid risks by formalizing the operations and centralizing decision-making in the organization. These are two of the main features linked to the bureaucracy (Mintzberg, 1979). The research allows to identify four different bureaucratic organizational typologies (insensitive, sensitive, participated and proactive) and different manager cultures (Perrow 1969; Nunkoo, R. and Smith, S. L. J. 2013, Ruhanen, L. 2013). It is necessary to extend the research to the other Italian regions located in the North and the South of the country for an accumulation of knowledge to improve the analyses and performances of IPTS and its bureaucracy.

Literature Review

The management of change process is a central topic in the broader issue of the bureaucracy. However, the achievement processes to implement organizational changes in bureaucracy have not received enough attention in academic research (Ongaro E., 2010; Raharjo K., Nurjannah, Solimun and Adji A. R. F., 2018). These issues are present also in IPTS (Boyne, Farrell, Law, Powell, & Walker, 2003; Kickert, 2007; Ongaro, 2010; Pollitt & Bouckaert, 2004; Tribe, J., and Liburd, J. 2016; Lamers, M., Van der Duim, V. R., and Spaargaren, G. 2017; Raharjo K., Nurjannah, Solimun and Adji A. R. F., 2018). As result, the achievement processes of change management at the regional level have not been properly developed in a lot of Italian geographical areas. Instead the theory on change management has usually been developed on private sector research applying the theory in a context-sensitive way during a change management process (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999; Pettigrew, Ferlie, & McKee, 1992; Pettigrew, Woodman, & Cameron, 2001) but unfortunately not in the context-sensitive way of bureaucratic theories (Kuipers et al., 2013). Despite the attention being paid to the Italian

bureaucracy, the literature has showed two considerable limits. The first is linked to the presence of a lot of studies based on qualitative methods (Ongaro E., 2010). Such studies emphasize the importance of the general framework at the national level of change management rather than on the implementation of achievement processes related to bureaucracy. A second limit regards the lack of empirical evidence concerning the specificity of change management of bureaucracy in IPTS. In this study for a better accumulation knowledge both topics have been dealt.

Bureaucracy and processes of change

In the years, many studies have examined the influence of managerial cultural factors on the outcomes of change management in the bureaucracy (Marcoulides and Heck 1993; Rosenthal and Masarech, 2003; Warrick, 2017). The studies on managerial culture within the bureaucracy have an old tradition. Starting from a classic approach, Weber (1922) distinguished eleven basic features of managerial culture in the bureaucratic public organization, but it is possible to reduce them to three main characteristics: *hierarchy* - each employee has a clearly defined role within a division of labor and his performance is evaluated by a direct superior. *Continuity* - the office constitutes full-time employment with a related salary and eventual possible perspectives of career. *Impersonality* - the work is conducted according to a general framework and checked by a superior. With reference to rational managerial culture, Simon (1947) argues that *“In the process of decision those alternatives are chosen which are considered to be appropriate means of reaching desired ends. Ends themselves, however, are often merely instrumental to more final objectives. We are thus led to the conception of a series, or hierarchy, of ends. Rationality has to do with the construction of means-ends chains of this kind”* (H. A. Simon, 1947). Crozier (1964), suggests that bureaucratic public organizations are characterized by the presence of a set of vicious circles and find their source in centralization and impersonality of the managerial culture: *The development of impersonal rules* - in order to be rational and democratic, bureaucracies try to develop a set of impersonal rules to cover all possible actions. The result, according to Crozier, is that hierarchical relationships weaken in the decision-making process and the bottom-up and top-down communications lose the power to govern the lower levels. *The centralization of decisions* - in order to maintain the impersonal nature of decision making, it is necessary to guarantee that the decision maker is protected from the influence of those who are affected by such decisions. The result is that there is no direct solution to the problem, within the organization, and furthermore the organization does not develop a knowledge oriented to the problem solution. In this way the decision-making process is delegated to some impartial central body. *The isolation of strata and group pressure within strata* - delegating to an impartial central body entails creating an organization that consists of a series of isolated strata. Within the strata is possible to underline two main characteristics: the first is that it represents the only defense for the individual against demands from other parts of the organization and the second one consists in allowing each group some degree of control over their own domain. The result is a mismatch between the single strata goals and the wider outcomes of the organization. *The development of parallel power relationships* - it is linked to the impossibility of the organization to check each stratum and group, furthermore the constant addition of impersonal rules and the progressive centralization of decision making create a strong uncertainty for the decision makers. The result is the creation of parallel power structures that give groups or individuals, in certain situations, disproportionate power in an organization.

A Bureaucratic public organization, according to the above-mentioned studies, is conceived as an organization that emphasizes hierarchy, rules, impersonality, routine and non-merit-based employment. Following these studies Weick and Quinn (1999) argue that the first step in implementing a management process change consists in an unfreezing of the principles of the

bureaucracy. Miner (1978, 1993,2005) proposes different organizational typologies highlighting the role of managerial culture also in the bureaucracy (Spangler, Tikhomirov, Sotak and Palrecha, 2014). The term, in Italy, is more often used to refer to the negative aspects of an organization rather than to the ideal organization type. This study, starting from the above described theories, intends to develop typologies of the bureaucracy in IPTS, underlining the role played by the *culture of* managers in paving the way for management change. The processes of change management allow the identification of different typologies of organizations underlining the importance of the influence of managerial culture in a bureaucratic public organization.

Case Study

Italian public tourism sector

Natural, archeological and cultural heritage assets of Italy are outstanding. National figures, concerning sites available to tourists can be synthesized as follows:

- 3.607 Museums;
- 802 Monuments;
- 330 Archaeological Sites.

More than 70% are owned and managed by the public sector. If the number of tourists is considered by geographic typology (Italian Tourist Council 2017), art cities are second only to seaside resorts:

- 38% seaside;
- 30% cities of artistic and historical interest;
- 15% mountain resorts;
- 8% lake resorts
- 4% hill and various resorts.

Annually, the three most visited public sector attractions are:

- The Colosseum, the Palatine Hill, and the Roman Forum;
- Excavations of Pompeii (Campania);
- Uffizi Gallery, (Florence, Tuscany).

In this context, we analyze the two regions with the largest number of tourist visits: Campania and Tuscany.

Case study context

In Europe, it is a cliché to state that the demand for tourism services has increased significantly over the last few decades. Many public organizations (Etzioni, 1964) have recognized (Chemin, 2016) a potential for adding to tourism supply in areas that were previously not considered attractive destinations (Aaker, Kumar, Day, 2003) for tourists. At the local level, (Beirman, 2003) particularly in Southern Europe, tourism has often been seen as a means of generating economic prosperity (Gartner, 2000) and playing a role previously attributed to manufacturing. Additionally, tourism can enable public authorities to achieve a variety of social objectives, such as improving employment (Commission of the European Union, 2016) and the physical environment of an area (Giddy J. K. & Webb N. L. 2016). CPTS and TPTS are within this track, in fact these two regions are driving for development of new investments by the European Union and other public actors that are changing the old manufacturing areas into the new and competitive tourist arena. (Hong W.-C. 2009). In this context (Aram, 2013) two different areas of the IPTS will be investigated. The IPTS is illustrative of the different, disjointed interests between administrative, organizational and managerial aspects (Simon, 1947). The IPTS must interact with the surrounding economic and social environment for which it should regulate the social (Merton, 1949) and economic processes. The IPTS is not the result of the simple addition of the performance of all units. On the contrary, it depends on the relationship, which exists among all tourism sector units, and the managers' decisions linked to it, among the

different economic and social goals and between these and the organizational and managerial actions (Thompson, 1967) of visible hand. To start from this assumption means abandoning the “one best way” of a tourism sector and replacing it within a change management process (Perrow, 1969). Campania, for e. g., has a very favorable climate and natural resources. The morphology favors the coastal area where the main points of interest are situated. The coast presents four gulfs including the one of Naples, which offers an excellent view of one of the active volcanos in continental Europe. Furthermore, secondary volcanic phenomena like hot springs are still present in the Neapolitan area like the Phlegrean Fields. Islands like Ischia, Procida and Capri are quite close, easily accessible via boat or hydrofoil from different parts of the coast and especially Naples port. There are many UNESCO sites throughout the region, including the recent addition of Naples’ historical city center. However, tourists who distribute wealth when visiting the region also require quality services during their stay. In certain cases, such as Pompeii and Capri, natural cultural attractions are complemented by quality services, which are also the result of management, professional skills and staff training. The specific statistical data concerning Campania is represented in Table 1. Particular, attention is addressed to the negative score concerning:

- presence variation – 11%;
- variation in Gross revenue, -12%;
- variation sector revenue, -5% foreign and -3% domestic.

Table 1 The specific statistical data concerning Campania

Territory		Accommodation	
Area Km ²	13.595.34	Beds	198.234
Resident population	5.831.461	Public sector beds as % of total (%)	5,7
Provinces	5		
Municipalities	551		
Density of inhabitants per Km ²	428,15		
Mobility		Presence of paying tourists	
Airports	2	Total presences	18.368.280
Railway km	1.252	Foreign (%)	40,6
State motorways km	1.285	Main nationalities of inbound tourists	USA - UK – D
Highways km	383	Average stay (days)	2,1
Ports	28	Presence variation 2016/2010	- 11%
		Total in Italy	98.602.605
Gross revenue		Sector revenue	
State cultural heritage (Euro)	31.362.067	Variation 2016/ 2010	- 5% foreing
Total in the South	34.038.022	Variation 2016/2010	- 3% domestic
Variation 2016/2010	- 12%		
Total in Italy	135.508.666		

Data elaborated from source: MiBacT 2017

The SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats) Analysis is an overview of IPTS. It involves the assessment of business organization's internal strengths and weaknesses, its opportunities for growth and improvement and the threats to its survival caused by the external environment. The SWOT analysis below synthesizes the sector in Table 2. It underlines structural problems linked to Threats, particularly:

- presence of investments from illegal revenue;
- long term emergencies in waste disposal issues and relative negative media impact.

About these problems regional action was implemented but results are disjointed and not effective.

Table 2 SWOT analysis Tourism Sector in Campania

Strength	Weakness
- youth accommodation - food and beverage Tours - cultural visits	- concentration of offer in certain areas, Naples and Salerno - inadequate value for money
Opportunities	Threats
- acquisition of certified brands of typical and protected products - acquisition of cultural events	- presence of investments from illegal revenue - long term emergencies in waste disposal issues and relative negative media impact

Our elaboration from TAB 1 source: MiBacT 2017

Tuscany has a very favorable climate and is rich in natural resources. The morphology favors the coastal area where most of the plains are situated. Tuscany has a triangular shape with a west coast on the Tyrrhenian Sea. There are mountain ranges that surround and cross the region and some fertile plains. Florence, Pisa and Empoli are among the most important Tuscan cities and are situated on the banks of the Arno River. In the inland areas there is tourism linked to agriculture because of the typical wine and food products. The islands, Elba and Giglio, are quite near and easily accessible, via boat or hydrofoil from different parts of the coast but mainly the port of Piombino. There are many UNESCO sites throughout the region. The specific statistical data concerning Tuscany is represented in **Table 3**. Particular attention is addressed to positive score concerning:

- presence variation +17%;
- variation Gross revenue + 37%;
- variation Sector revenue, foreign + 18%, domestic + 14%.

Table 3 The specific statistical data concerning Tuscany

Territory	Accommodation
Area Km ² 22.994	Beds 187.881
Resident population 3.753 million	Public sector beds as % of total (%) 7.7
Provinces 10	
Municipalities 279	
Density of inhabitants per Km ² 163	

Mobility	Presence of paying tourists
Airports 3	Total presences 44.000.00
Railway km 1476	Foreign (%) 47,5
State motorways km 1254	Main nationalities of inbound tourists USA - UK - D
Highways km 641	Jap - China
Ports 41	Average stay (days) 4,7
	Presence variation 2016/2010 17%
	Total in Italy 98.602.605
Gross revenue	Sector revenue
State cultural heritage (Euro) 38.392.097	Variation 2016/ 2010 18% foreign
Total in the north 44.138.822	Variation 2016/2010 14% domestic
Variation 2016/2010 37%	
Total in Italy 135.508.666	

Data elaborated from source: MiBacT 2017

The SWOT analysis below synthesizes the sector in Table 4. It underlines structural problems linked to Threats, particularly:

- coastal erosion;
- worsening conditions of the sea water.

Concerning these problems regional and national action was implemented but results are disjointed and not effective.

Table 4 SWOT analysis Tourism Sector in Tuscany

Strength	Weakness
- Cultural and natural heritage - Agricultural production quality and certified, and the food and wine - Brand "Tuscany" & Tuscan cities inland Presence of numerous territories certified	- Lack of a network of urban and suburban public transport - Lack of public aggregation places - Depopulation and aging population seasonality
Opportunities	Threats
- Increase the synergies between territories (coast-hinterland) - Possibility to exploit alternative types of tourism/tourism products differentiated but complementary - Exploiting the demand for green tourism	- Loss of traditions and identity - Coastal erosion - Worsening conditions of the sea water.

Our elaboration from Tab 3 source: MiBacT 2017

Campania and Tuscany are representative of IPTS with more than 1/3 of total presences.

Northern vs southern IPTS

A change in the relationship between the northern and southern Italian public sectors (Ouerfelli, 2010) is necessary. These changes can affect the attractiveness of destinations and

the consequences of tourism development on social and physical environments (Chen, Var, 2010). New logic and change management processes are linked to the application of bureaucracy theory in the IPTS (Blackman D., Kennedy M. & Ritchie B. 2011). Such issues, include:

- the characteristics of the tasks that the public tourism sector is supposed to carry out;
- the normative foundation of their work and;
- in this context, some strategic organizational and managerial elements are considered in order to improve management and managers. These elements are referred to the task context and the normative context.

The task context

The tourist's experience is typically produced by two circuits. The first relates to travel patterns and motivations. The second is more diffuse and complicated. It concerns the local managers' goal for which the specific services can be seen as a means and an end. In this latter approach, tourism is not about an individual's concerns, but rather about the reproduction and development of their country's culture. In this way, IPTS carries out both aggregative and integrative functions. On the one hand, it must take as a point of departure the citizens' needs (aggregation); on the other, it socializes and regulates the citizens' behavior (integration).

The normative context

The normative context contains the considerations, principles and demands to which the managers must generally relate. Therefore, there are varying elements, all of which can be seen as restrictions on internal processes and the way in which services are produced and distributed. The issues are related to resources use, productivity, efficiency and quality of services.

Methodology

Starting from data MIBACT 2017, Table 1 and Table 3, the SWOT analysis results, have been presented in Table 2 and Table 4. The SWOT analysis has been utilized to build up open interviews with 24 privileged witnesses, 12 CPTS and 12 TPTS, 4 for each of the 3 areas: coast, middle, inland, that make up the sector. The decision to divide the region into three main areas is dictated by the different orientation of the management culture (Schein, 1985) concerning the privileged witnesses. From these interviews were emerged the following strategic variables (Blau, 1971). Motivational factors and working organization are essential, knowing how and why to motivate employees is an important managerial skill. Furthermore, IPTS legislation is strategic (Ruhanen L. 2008) in order to formulate a legal and regulatory framework for the sustainable development and management of tourism. Job stability (Lillo-Bañuls A. & Casado-Díaz J. M., 2015), is also an important element. Furthermore, investment in information technology (ICT) (Torrent-Sellens J., Ficapal-Cusí P., Boada-Grau J. Vigil-Colet A. 2016), the role of private organization (Tse T.S.M. & Prideaux B. 2017), the allotment of duties and managerial culture are major human factors (Prayag G. & Hosany S. 2015) at the organizational level. Furthermore, by privileged witnesses has been possible Fig. 1 that show the IPTS. From the emerged variables by the interviews to the 24 privileged witnesses, a sample of Italian public managers was selected during May 2017, the interviews started during September 2017. The high number of managers in two different regions and in different areas in the regions, 800 in CPTS and 800 in TPTS required significant amount of time in order to establish contact and make visits. A large proportion of the interviews (70 per cent) was undertaken in the Local public agencies of the two regions conducted inside the organization and the remainder (30 per cent) by skype interview. From Fig.1, it can be said that the two regions are characterized by:

Fig. 1. Italian public tourism sector (our elaboration from source Mibact 2017)

- the presence of one large public agency in each region and the presence of few large companies (provider area, see the SWOT analysis Table 2 and 4);
- the presence of small firms (allotment of duties area, see the SWOT analysis Table 2 and 4) with at most ten employees and,
- the presence of a consumer goods area (see Table 1 and Table 3).

The first and second areas (see Fig. 1) have been investigated using a questionnaire that takes into account three different context of analysis:

- social background variables;
- productivity variables;
- efficiency variables.

The second and third parts of the questionnaire comprised 30 pre - developed, 15 for each part, Likert statements, designed to measure the productivity and efficiency variables. Specifically, respondents were asked to indicate the level of criticism on a seven-point scale, ranging from “strong criticism” (7) to “low criticism” (1) by different items of the second and third parts. The 30 Likert statements were explored by principal components factor analysis and varimax rotation, which resulted in a four - factor solution, two for each region. The purpose of the factor analysis (Hair and others, 1995) was to combine the statements into a set of factors that were deemed to represent a first organizational type linked to the interviews of managers in different regions. The internal consistency of each factor was examined by Cronbach’s alpha tests. All the alpha coefficients were above 0.5, which means that high correlation existed between the items. The collected data were statistically analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0.

Empirical results

The results were obtained by questioning a sample of managers from Campania and Tuscany. The sample distribution by geographical and education factors, is show in tables 5 and 6. Table 6 shows the general lack of tertiary sector educational qualifications among the staff.

Table 5 Managers by region

Campania public managers (South Italy)	Tuscany public managers (North Italy)
33% on the coast	33% on the coast
33% in the middle	33% in the middle
33% inland	33% inland
Total managers 800	Total managers 800

Within the three macro areas, culture and service (Selznick, 1953, Sasser et. al., 1978) orientation is homogeneous in relation to the school curriculum and previous experience in the field. Table 6 shows the number of graduates for the two regions. “No educational level” in Campania, is the item with the greatest number of responses. In Tuscany a degree in management, law, engineering, cultural heritage (also these prevail for Campania) and Secondary school diploma represent 58 per cent of the responses.

Table 6 Managers education level by region

Campania public managers South Italy	Tuscany public managers North Italy
University 10%	University 30%
Secondary high school 25%	Secondary high school 28%
Junior high school 20%	Junior high school 31%
No education level 45%	No education level 19%
Total 100% (70% male)	Total 100% (80% male)

The purpose of the factor analysis, which resulted in a three factors solution, was to combine the statements into a set of factors that were deemed to represent the organizational types linked to the interviews of managers. Specifically, items with higher loadings, 16 factors, (see table 7) were considered (alpha coefficients above 0.5) as more important and as having a greater influence (Hair et al., 1995) on organizational types.

Table 7 Factor analysis Italian public managers

Factor names and items	Mean	S.D.	Factor Loading	Alpha
Improving productivity Campania Managers	5.0			0.83
Motivational factor to entry	5.25	1.57	0.78	
The role of public management	5.14	1.59	0.65	
Control of public sector	5.19	1.36	0.58	
Coordination of public sector	5.61	1.43	0.61	
Improving productivity Tuscany Managers	5.73			0.90
Relations customers – allotment of duties	5.19	1.37	0.53	
Low level of information technology	5.15	1.37	0.49	
Private control	6.15	1.11	0.81	
Private coordination	6.25	1.23	0.88	
Improving efficiency Campania Managers	5.26			0.80
Work organization as problem	5.19	1.54	0.75	
Mutual help relation with other managers	5.00	1.04	0.62	
Job stability	5.17	1.13	0.52	
Salary	5.13	1.11	0.69	
Improving efficiency Tuscany Managers	5.73			0.81
Managerial culture	5.71	1.24	0.75	
Quality of service	5.16	1.51	0.72	
Credit and information by banks	5.23	1.37	0.54	
Public legislation	5.33	1.47	0.64	

Managers have been asked what the critical points to improve productivity are. The results are categorized in table 8. Southern Italian managers (Campania) emphasized motivational factors to entry, especially incentives for productivity and training, and then factors described as ‘the form of management’ and ‘coordination of the tourism sector’. Northern Italian public managers (Tuscany) considered the first element to be ‘coordination’ and ‘control of public sector’. Both groups of managers underline the necessity of a new normative context and strongly criticize the role of the Italian Government.

Table 8 Factor loading items linked to the critical points for improving productivity

Campania Managers	Tuscany Managers
Motivational factor to entry (0.78)	relation customer – allotment of duties (0.53)
The role of public management (0.65)	low level of information technology (0.49)
control of public sector (0.58)	private control (0.81)
coordination of public sector (0.61)	private coordination (0.88)

The critical factors to efficiency items (Campania, see table 9) are: ‘work organization’, ‘mutual help relationships with other agencies’ and ‘salary’. Managers underline the absence of hierarchical influences and ‘professionalism’ into the service supply. They also point out the need to improve mutual relationships with other managers. The managers underline the modalities by which the different members of the organization undertake their specific tasks, professional functions and roles. The salary is the last element; managers argue that individual economic reward should be taken into account to improve productivity and efficiency. Northern managers, from Tuscany, (see table 9) underline the importance of ‘managerial culture’ and ‘quality of service’ in terms of paying more attention to the specific managerial culture of the sector and the needs of its users. One important bottle neck is quality of service in the relations

between customers and the allocation of duties: with reference to the need for a quick response about the coordination and control of information flows.

Table 9 Factor loading items linked to the critical points for improving efficiency

Campania managers	Tuscany Managers
Working organization as a problem (0.75)	managerial culture (0.75)
Mutual help relation with other manager (0.62)	quality of service (0.72)
Job stability (0.52)	credit and information by banks (0.54)
Salary (0.69)	public legislation (0.64)

Starting from tables 8 and 9, the data shows four different organizational types:

- insensitive organization;
- sensitive organization;
- participated organization;
- proactive organization.

In the insensitive organization the main characteristics refer to low attention to the identification of the user's needs, and to productivity and efficiency. This configuration is present in a large part of Campania, particularly inland. This type of organization takes into account the following factors to improve productivity:

- motivational factors to entry (0.78);
- the role of public management (0.65),

and improving efficiency:

- work organization as problem (0.75);
- salary (0.69).

The sensitive organization shows interest in the knowledge of the user's needs, productivity and efficiency. This configuration is present in Campania on the coast and inland in Tuscany. In these areas, the organization takes into account the following factors to improve productivity:

- control of public sector (0.58);
- coordination of public sector (0.61);

improving efficiency:

- mutual help in relations with other managers (0.62);
- job stability (0.52).

Participated organization in the middle of Tuscany takes into account the following factors for improving productivity:

- relations with customers - allotment of duties (0.53);
- low level of information technology (0.49);

improving efficiency:

- public legislation (0.64);
- credit and information by bank (0.54).

The proactive organization shows great interest in the user's requests, productivity and efficiency. This configuration is present in a large part of the Tuscany coast. This type of organization takes into account the following factors for improving productivity:

- private control (0.81);
- private coordination (0.88);

improving efficiency:

- managerial culture (0.75);
- quality of service (0.72).

Discussion, Limitations and Implications for Future Research

The results of this study highlight the coexistence of classic bureaucracy and a new form of bureaucracy (Ongaro 2010, Ouerfelli 2010, Warrick 2017, Raharjo et al. 2018). In this context, according to the literature (Boyne, Farrell, Law, Powell, & Walker, 2003; Kickert, 2007), change management is a topic related to the bureaucracy (Pollitt & Bouckaert, 2004; Tribe, J., and Liburd, J. 2016). This study contributes to create a pool of knowledge related to change management, particularly in IPTS, by underlining the relevant elements within different bureaucratic typologies. The four organizational typologies, the insensitive, sensitive, participated and proactive organization, highlighted in the empirical results how managers have strategic influence on the services productivity and efficiency. In Campania and Tuscany, south and north Italy, two different approaches emerge. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the use of change management process within the IPTS. On one hand, this takes the form of importing ideas and methods developed in and for the private sector. The assumption is that the private sector is better than the public sector in some specific ways: private sector organizations are more cost conscious, more inclined to implement modern personnel management and more capable of developing corporate culture as a steering instrument. Such a debate considers the incentives for productivity and particularly the necessity to create some reliable measures of management efficiency in the IPTS. On the other hand, there is an interest in the use of change management process in the study of the IPTS. Here the aim is somewhat different. The change management process should be verified, considering the real behaviors and managers' bureaucratic culture. After this first step the theory helps us to better understand the IPTS. In the literature review – case study context - and empirical results, the managers of two different geographic areas have two completely different approaches: in Tuscany the main variables are those of the private control and coordination, the importance of ICT and allotment of duties. Campania instead, always improving its productivity, underlines the importance of control and coordination of public sector, the motivational factor and the role of public management. In order to improve the efficiency, the two regions underline different variables set that for Tuscany is the managerial culture, quality of service, role of bank and public legislation. In Campania instead, such different variables set is working organization, mutual help, job stability and salary. The difference between the regions within the same country highlights that despite the profound differences in managerial culture, both attract a growing number of tourists. Operative and theoretical action are important to improve the IPTS. At operative level some organizational actions are strategic for managers in different regions. Particularly a cross contamination between managers in the different regions could be an interesting operative approach to improve efficiency and productivity in Campania by large part of Tuscany managers from the coast. It will be important to implement a governance idea of IPTS. In addition, there are different configurations in the same areas. The research was limited to only 2 regions (North and South) located in Italy out of a total of 22 regions. So, it is necessary to extend the research to other Italian regions located in the North and South of Italy. Possible measures to address change management problems (Lamers, M., Van der Duim, V. R., and Spaargaren, G. 2017; Raharjo K., Nurjannah, Solimun and Adji A. R. F., 2018) linked to the bureaucracy could be identified in further research, analysis of good practices and cross contamination of proactive managers with the participated and insensitive managers. This process can be identified as an achievement for IPTS and its bureaucracy (Weber, 1922 Simon, 1947, Crozier, 1964, Weick and Quinn 1969).

Conclusion

It will be important to implement a change management process in IPTS and its bureaucracy. Campania and Tuscany are important for the economic development of the IPTS. A change management process is possible.

Making a change means taking into account the different experiences of the bureaucracy in public organization, in each of these broad areas in which there are significant differences in relation to the location and culture. It is important to modify operational values and decisions. Four organizational typologies emerge from research: insensitive organization; sensitive organization; participated organization; proactive organization. Insensitive organization is representative of large parts of Campania, particularly inland and middle. The managers underline the importance of motivational factors to entry and work organization as a problem, in this configuration the high number of “no educational level”, is a problem to improve efficiency and productivity. The second configuration underlines the importance of mutual help relation with other managers. Here the need is for a managerial approach between different stories, cultures, a tight confrontation to understand what the best strategies to follow and implement are. It is worth noting that in these two configurations the presence of Campania is exhausted and therefore it is placed between the insensate and sensitive configuration, while here we have the inland of Tuscany characterized by no educational level. In the third configuration there is only Tuscany, in particular the center. The need for greater investment in ICT and the low level of information technology were considered interesting variables to improve productivity. The proactive organization is present in large part of the coast in Tuscany, where there are managers with a degree in management, engineering and law and there is a family firm structure with excellent control and coordination of activities. Managerial culture and quality of service are best practice. Cross-contamination is needed between the managers of the two regions. Proactive organizational managers should support a particularly insensitive organization such as the one present in the inland of Campania. Cross contamination is important for change. The national policy on tourism, as a governance idea is a strategic action parallel to the first one. These operative and theoretical levers can represent an interesting organizational and economic mix to improve the IPTS. It is a diagnosis that, strategically implemented, reflects the nature of the different systems and contributes to the discovery of key strategic areas where a change could produce a better performance for the service and users. Values and culture of the bureaucracy are present in a part of Tuscany. The role of the IPTS is an open question and therefore, in the diagnosis of change management process there is no “one best way”. Such a view rejects a stance whereby the bureaucracy could be regarded as ultimately unchangeable. It must instead be seen as under constant development and re-interpretation.

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